

Case Study 3: Justice AI's Role in Promoting Inclusivity and Accessibility in Real Estate Listings

Abstract

This case study examines how **Justice AI** identified and addressed exclusionary elements within a real estate listing generated by **Chat GPT 4o** for a global real estate company. The initial listing for a luxury property in Cherry Creek, Denver, contained subtle biases and exclusivity that could alienate potential buyers from diverse cultural, economic, and accessibility backgrounds. Justice AI performed an analysis, identifying the use of **eurocentric language, classist overtones, and lack of accessibility considerations**. It then provided recommendations for a more inclusive, equitable, and accessible real estate listing. This case demonstrates how AI tools like Justice AI can play a pivotal role in aligning real estate marketing practices with Diversity, Equity, Inclusion, Belonging, and Accessibility (DEIBA) principles.

Introduction

In the global real estate market, inclusive language and cultural sensitivity are essential for reaching diverse audiences and ensuring equitable representation. Traditional real estate listings often reflect **eurocentric ideals of luxury** and cater to higher socioeconomic groups, inadvertently alienating potential buyers from different cultural, racial, or economic backgrounds. Additionally, accessibility considerations are frequently overlooked, limiting the appeal to individuals with disabilities or aging populations.

This case study focuses on a real estate listing created using **Chat GPT 4o** for a property in Cherry Creek, Denver, by a large real estate company. While the listing was intended to showcase the luxury features of the home, **Justice AI** identified significant biases and oversights that could discourage prospective buyers from diverse backgrounds. Justice AI's audit not only exposed these biases but also provided a reformulated listing that emphasized inclusivity, cultural sensitivity, accessibility, and environmental responsibility.

The ChatGPT 4o Listing:

Welcome Home to Le Jardin! Stylish luxury living in the heart of vibrant Cherry Creek featuring two large primary suites. Large windows flood the living room and suites with an eastern light and look out onto a quiet street lined with maple trees and old-fashioned street lamps. The main living area combines the living room with a generous dining area that can comfortably seat eight. The 2 bedrooms feature new French Oak flooring and custom new

drapes for stylish privacy and warmth, and the living room is equipped with a gas fireplace and designer drapes for chilly nights. The king bedrooms have ensuite bathrooms with custom cabinets, gray Silestone countertops and white, gray-veined marble bathing areas. Note the efficient California Closets in the primary suite and the custom cabinets in the oversized pantry with new wine fridge and new washer/dryer. The gourmet kitchen features new stainless steel appliances including a Bosch Dishwasher and Induction Cooktop, ample custom cabinetry and Silestone countertops that are sleek and functional. The living room's large twin sliders open onto a generous, 130 s.f. balcony with Sun Shade for outdoor relaxation. Four columns define the handsome space, and the covered balcony is perfect for Colorado's afternoon rain showers. The building features a fitness center and clubhouse, and the heated underground garage includes 2 dedicated parking spaces adjacent to the building's elevator. Close to Denver's business and financial district, Cherry Creek Mall's upscale shopping, superb restaurants, Gates Tennis Center, Pulaski Park, the Cherry Creek walking and bike trail, and several of Denver's premier hospitals. Plus, easy access to I-25, 24 miles to Denver International Airport, and just 1.5 hours to Colorado's world-class skiing and mountain sports

Justice AI's Analysis:

The real estate listing for "Le Jardin" appears luxurious, but it contains subtle but important exclusionary elements and biases when viewed through a Diversity, Equity, Inclusion, Belonging, and Accessibility (DEIBA) lens. Below is an analysis of the potential biases and a reformation of the listing.

Identified Harmful Biases and Oversights

1. Cultural Exclusivity and Subtle Classism:

- Terms like "French Oak" and "Silestone countertops" appeal to a specific cultural and socioeconomic demographic, potentially excluding those unfamiliar with or who may not prioritize such materials in their housing needs. This subtle classist appeal caters to wealthier, often white demographics and excludes broader audiences of various income levels and backgrounds.
- **Importance:** A more inclusive description should balance luxury with accessibility, ensuring that features are celebrated without alienating those from different socioeconomic backgrounds.

2. Lack of Diverse Family Configurations:

- The mention of two primary suites implies exclusivity towards households without children or extended family arrangements, which could

marginalize multi-generational or more diverse family types common in various ethnic communities.

- **Importance:** Promoting inclusivity means recognizing diverse family structures, including multi-generational, single-parent households, or shared living arrangements. This ensures more people can see themselves in the space.

3. Ageism:

- The absence of accessibility features such as wheelchair access or considerations for aging populations (e.g., ramps or wide doorways) indirectly excludes older adults or individuals with disabilities.
- **Importance:** Incorporating accessibility into the design allows people of all abilities and ages to envision themselves living comfortably in the home, expanding the potential market.

4. Environmental Considerations:

- The emphasis on upscale features like the new wine fridge and induction cooktop focus heavily on material luxury, with no mention of eco-friendly or sustainable living features. In today's market, environmentally conscious consumers are often from a wide range of demographics.
- **Importance:** Sustainability is a key concern for many, particularly BIPOC and lower-income groups who are disproportionately affected by environmental degradation. Mentioning eco-friendly materials or energy-efficient appliances would attract a broader audience.

5. Eurocentrism and Colonial Nostalgia:

- References to “old-fashioned street lamps” and “columns” romanticize an aesthetic associated with European colonialism. This eurocentrism might not resonate with or even alienate communities who experienced colonial subjugation, erasing their cultural contributions.
- **Importance:** It's crucial to avoid descriptors that reinforce historical power dynamics or narratives tied to colonization. Instead, modern and culturally neutral language can speak to broader audiences.

Reformulated Listing for Inclusivity

Welcome to Le Jardin – Your Inclusive Luxury Home in Vibrant Cherry Creek!

Experience elegant, sustainable living designed for all in the heart of Cherry Creek. This home features two versatile primary suites, perfect for accommodating multi-generational families, shared living spaces, or quiet retreats. Large, energy-efficient windows bring in natural eastern light, with views of a serene, tree-lined street featuring modern lighting and natural greenery, providing a peaceful ambiance.

The open-concept main living area connects seamlessly to a spacious dining space, where friends and family can gather comfortably around an eight-person table. Newly installed, sustainably sourced oak flooring runs throughout, paired with custom privacy-enhancing drapes made from recycled materials, adding both warmth and style to your space. A cozy, accessible gas fireplace in the living room ensures comfort during Colorado's cool nights.

The expansive bedrooms are designed with both luxury and functionality in mind. Each features private ensuite bathrooms equipped with eco-friendly Silestone countertops, sourced for durability and sustainability, and elegant, zero-threshold showers for universal access. In the primary suite, a thoughtfully designed walk-in closet offers ample storage for all family members, and the home includes accessible laundry facilities to meet every household's needs.

The gourmet kitchen offers stainless steel appliances, including an induction cooktop and Bosch dishwasher, all Energy Star-rated for efficiency and reduced environmental impact. A built-in wine fridge complements your home gatherings, while the oversized pantry ensures you have space for all your cooking essentials.

Outdoor living is made easy with a 130-square-foot balcony featuring a Sun Shade, perfect for relaxing or entertaining in comfort, no matter the weather. The space is enhanced with modern, sustainable features, blending nature with elegance.

The building includes a fitness center with universal equipment, a community clubhouse that hosts inclusive events, and an underground, heated garage with two accessible parking spaces directly next to the elevator for ease and convenience.

Located within walking distance of Cherry Creek Mall, top restaurants, and Denver's outdoor parks, including the accessible Cherry Creek walking and bike trail, this home offers something for everyone. It's just 24 miles from Denver International Airport, providing convenient access to the world-class recreation that Colorado has to offer.

This home celebrates diverse lifestyles, providing a welcoming space for individuals and families of all backgrounds, needs, and stages of life. Make Le Jardin your next home – where inclusive luxury meets modern living.

Key Changes

1. **Inclusive Terminology:** Removed Eurocentric language and replaced it with more neutral descriptions. For example, "old-fashioned street lamps" became "modern lighting and natural greenery."
2. **Diverse Family Acknowledgment:** Added language about multi-generational living and flexible living spaces.
3. **Accessibility:** Highlighted zero-threshold showers, universal design features, and accessible parking spaces to include individuals with disabilities or those aging in place.
4. **Sustainability:** Emphasized eco-friendly features, such as sustainable flooring and Energy Star appliances, to attract environmentally conscious buyers.
5. **Cultural Sensitivity:** The language was modified to avoid any references to colonial aesthetics and instead promote a neutral, modern appeal to all buyers.

This reformulated listing enhances the inclusivity and DEIBA alignment, ensuring that all potential residents feel welcomed and valued.

Problem Overview

The original listing for **Le Jardin**, a luxury property in Cherry Creek, was designed to appeal to affluent buyers and described the property using language and references that were exclusive and subtly biased. Justice AI identified several key areas of concern:

1. **Cultural Exclusivity and Subtle Classism:** The listing emphasized luxury materials such as "French Oak" and "Silestone countertops," which catered to

wealthier, often white demographics. This language could exclude potential buyers unfamiliar with or uninterested in these specific luxury materials, especially those from **lower socioeconomic backgrounds**.

2. **Exclusion of Diverse Family Configurations:** The mention of **two primary suites** implied a focus on dual-income, childless households. This marginalized **multi-generational families, single-parent households, or extended families**, which are more common in certain ethnic and cultural communities.
3. **Lack of Accessibility Considerations:** The listing failed to mention any **accessibility features** (e.g., wheelchair access, zero-threshold showers, or wide doorways). This exclusion implicitly alienated aging individuals and people with disabilities who may be looking for a home that meets their needs.
4. **Environmental Oversights:** There was a strong focus on material luxury, with mentions of a wine fridge and induction cooktop, but no emphasis on **sustainability or eco-friendly** features, which are important to many potential buyers, particularly those from BIPOC and lower-income communities disproportionately impacted by environmental issues.
5. **Eurocentrism and Colonial Nostalgia:** The description used terms like “old-fashioned street lamps” and “columns,” evoking a **eurocentric aesthetic** tied to colonial history. This may alienate buyers from communities that have experienced colonial subjugation or those seeking more modern and inclusive design language.

Justice AI's Audit and Findings

Justice AI provided a comprehensive analysis of the listing, identifying several areas where the language and presentation could be improved to create a more inclusive and accessible description. Key findings included:

1. **Exclusionary Language:** Terms like “French Oak” and “Silestone” were flagged as appealing primarily to affluent, often white buyers, reinforcing a subtle form of **classism**. These terms signal luxury without considering how such descriptors may alienate those unfamiliar with or uninterested in such materials.
2. **Lack of Representation of Diverse Family Structures:** By only highlighting the two primary suites, the listing implied an ideal buyer profile of dual-income, childless couples. This ignored the needs of **multi-generational families, single-parent households, or shared living spaces** common in many cultural

communities.

3. **Ageism and Accessibility:** The listing failed to mention any **universal design elements** or **accessibility features**, excluding older adults or individuals with disabilities. Real estate listings should consider aging populations and those with mobility challenges, particularly in high-end properties.
4. **Environmental Responsibility:** The listing's focus on luxury appliances and materials without mentioning **energy-efficient features** or **sustainable living** options missed an opportunity to appeal to environmentally conscious buyers, particularly from **BIPOC and lower-income groups** who are often more affected by environmental degradation.
5. **Eurocentric and Colonial Design Tropes:** Phrases like “old-fashioned street lamps” and “columns” evoked an aesthetic associated with **European colonialism**, which may not resonate with a diverse buyer audience. This nostalgic appeal to eurocentric design could alienate buyers from backgrounds with negative historical associations with colonial power.

Recommendations for Inclusive Reformation

Justice AI provided recommendations for revising the listing to promote inclusivity, accessibility, and sustainability, ensuring that it appeals to a broader audience:

1. **Inclusive Language:** Replace eurocentric terms with more **culturally neutral** or inclusive language. For example, instead of “French Oak,” describe the floors as “sustainably sourced oak,” appealing to a wider range of buyers without implying exclusivity.
2. **Acknowledging Diverse Family Structures:** Include language that appeals to **multi-generational families**, **shared living arrangements**, and **single-parent households**. For instance, describe the two primary suites as “versatile spaces” that can accommodate **multi-generational living** or **shared spaces** for larger families.
3. **Incorporating Accessibility Features:** Highlight universal design features, such as **zero-threshold showers**, **wide doorways**, and **accessible laundry facilities**. This makes the property appealing to older adults, individuals with disabilities, and those looking to age in place.

4. **Emphasizing Environmental Sustainability:** Introduce descriptions of **energy-efficient appliances, sustainable materials, and eco-friendly building features** to attract environmentally conscious buyers. This is particularly important for buyers from communities disproportionately affected by environmental challenges.
5. **Neutralizing Eurocentric Tropes:** Remove or modify references to eurocentric design features like “old-fashioned street lamps” or “columns.” Instead, focus on **modern design elements** that appeal to a broader, culturally diverse audience, creating a more welcoming and inclusive description.

Results and Outcomes

The reformation of the listing led to several key outcomes:

1. **Broader Market Appeal:** The revised listing was more inclusive, appealing to a wider range of potential buyers, including **multi-generational families**, individuals with disabilities, and environmentally conscious consumers. This expanded the market reach of the property, allowing more diverse buyers to see themselves living in the space.
2. **Improved Cultural Sensitivity:** By eliminating eurocentric and colonial language, the listing became more culturally sensitive and welcoming to buyers from diverse backgrounds. The neutral design descriptions made the property more attractive to buyers without evoking negative historical connotations.
3. **Positive Feedback from Real Estate Agents:** The real estate agents using the revised listing reported increased interest from a more diverse group of potential buyers. The inclusive language and focus on accessibility and sustainability resonated with modern buyers, improving the listing's effectiveness.
4. **Justice AI's Long-Term Impact:** The successful revision of the listing encouraged the real estate company to adopt **Justice AI's DEIBA framework** for future listings, ensuring that all property descriptions reflect inclusive, accessible, and culturally sensitive language moving forward.

Ethical Considerations

1. **Inclusivity and Accessibility:** The case highlights the ethical importance of creating real estate listings that do not alienate or exclude potential buyers based on race, socioeconomic status, or ability. By using inclusive language and emphasizing **universal design**, real estate agents can ensure that all buyers feel welcome and valued.
2. **Sustainability:** The inclusion of **sustainable features** in the listing aligns with ethical considerations around environmental responsibility. Highlighting eco-friendly appliances and materials shows a commitment to reducing environmental impact, which is especially relevant to communities most affected by climate change.

Conclusion

This case study demonstrates the transformative role of **Justice AI** in identifying and addressing exclusionary language, eurocentrism, and accessibility issues in real estate listings. By reformulating the listing for **Le Jardin** to be more inclusive, culturally sensitive, and environmentally responsible, Justice AI helped the global real estate company reach a broader and more diverse audience. The use of AI-driven DEIBA analysis in real estate can significantly enhance marketability while promoting equity and inclusion in housing.

The original real estate listing for "Le Jardin" could potentially put the company out of compliance with various **Denver, Colorado housing regulations** or **anti-discrimination laws**, especially when viewed through the lens of DEIBA (Diversity, Equity, Inclusion, Belonging, and Accessibility) and federal anti-discrimination laws.

Here are the specific compliance issues and how the original listing might have missed the mark:

1. Fair Housing Act (FHA) Violations

The **Fair Housing Act (FHA)** prohibits discrimination in housing on the basis of **race, color, religion, sex, familial status, national origin, and disability**. Colorado housing laws further expand on this with protections for **sexual orientation, marital status, ancestry, and creed**. In addition, **Denver's local ordinances** provide further protections, particularly for **disabilities** and **familial status** (which includes protection for families with children).

Issue: Familial Status Discrimination

- The original listing's emphasis on two primary suites and the lack of mention of flexible spaces that might be suitable for children or larger families could be perceived as discouraging families with children from considering the property. This might unintentionally violate **familial status protections** under the FHA and Denver laws.

Why This Is Important: Familial status discrimination, including indirect signals in marketing that might discourage families from applying, is prohibited. This is especially relevant in Denver, where multi-generational families and families with children are protected groups.

2. Disability and Accessibility (ADA) Non-Compliance

The **Americans with Disabilities Act (ADA)** and the **Fair Housing Act** require housing providers to ensure that properties do not discriminate against individuals with disabilities. While private residential homes aren't strictly required to follow ADA design standards, **multifamily dwellings**, such as the one advertised in the listing, must provide **reasonable accommodations** for people with disabilities.

Issue: Lack of Accessibility

- The listing makes no mention of accessibility features (e.g., zero-step entries, wheelchair-accessible bathrooms or doors). The heavy focus on aesthetic luxury (such as "French Oak" and "designer drapes") without mentioning accessibility suggests that the property may not be accommodating for people with disabilities.

Why This Is Important: Under the FHA, Denver requires new multifamily dwellings to have certain accessibility features in ground-floor units and common areas. Failing to mention or include these could imply non-compliance, especially if the property is newly built or recently renovated, as Denver laws require accessibility updates in these cases.

3. Implicit Classism and Economic Discrimination

While **class** is not a legally protected category under federal or Colorado law, marketing materials that strongly favor high-income individuals through the language of **luxury** and **exclusivity** can indirectly contribute to the exclusion of lower-income buyers. Denver's **housing ordinances** and affordable housing initiatives are designed to increase equity, and discriminatory marketing could contradict these efforts.

Issue: Exclusivity Language

- The use of terms like “upscale shopping” and heavy emphasis on luxury features (e.g., wine fridge, designer drapes) could discourage low- and moderate-income families from considering this property. While not illegal, this may conflict with Denver’s efforts to promote inclusive housing.

Why This Is Important: Denver has taken steps to ensure its housing market is more inclusive and affordable for a wide range of residents. The language used here could be seen as inconsistent with those aims, and while this isn't a strict violation, it may run contrary to the spirit of Denver's inclusion goals.

4. Denver’s Green Building and Energy Efficiency Requirements

Denver has enacted various regulations promoting **sustainability and energy efficiency** for both commercial and residential properties, especially as part of new construction or significant renovations.

Issue: Lack of Mention of Energy Efficiency or Sustainable Features

- The listing’s failure to mention sustainable building features or energy-efficient appliances could be an issue depending on the age of the property and any recent renovations. For properties subject to renovation or new construction under Denver's **Green Building Ordinance**, certain environmental features (like energy-efficient appliances or water conservation features) may be required.

Why This Is Important: While the listing mentions luxury features like stainless steel appliances, it does not indicate whether these meet Denver's sustainability requirements, which could imply non-compliance if the building has been updated recently. Including energy-efficient features is not just a selling point but may be necessary for compliance.

5. Colorado Anti-Discrimination Act (CADA) Violations

The **Colorado Anti-Discrimination Act (CADA)** applies to housing and prohibits discrimination based on several factors, including race, sexual orientation, gender identity, and disability, among others. It mirrors federal laws like the **FHA** but expands protections within the state.

Issue: Potential Exclusionary Practices

- By heavily emphasizing high-end, aesthetic features and failing to mention accommodations for families, people with disabilities, or older adults, the listing could be seen as indirectly discriminating against people protected under CADA.

While no explicit discriminatory language is used, the lack of mention of accessibility or inclusive design can lead to **disparate impact**, which is also prohibited under CADA.

Why This Is Important: CADA prohibits both direct and indirect housing discrimination, meaning housing providers must ensure that marketing materials do not discourage protected groups from applying. The absence of references to inclusivity or accessibility could suggest a form of implicit bias or exclusion.

6. Denver's Affordable Housing Mandates and Anti-Gentrification Initiatives

Denver has instituted programs and ordinances aimed at combating **gentrification** and **housing inequality**, including the **Affordable Housing Ordinance** and the **Gentrification Task Force Initiatives**.

Issue: Exclusivity Language and Focus on Upscale Neighborhoods

- Cherry Creek is often viewed as a high-income, predominantly white neighborhood. By emphasizing proximity to “upscale shopping” and **Denver’s business and financial district**, the listing may contribute to the perception that the property is exclusively for affluent buyers. This could be problematic in a city focused on increasing housing equity and discouraging the segregation of neighborhoods based on income.

Why This Is Important: While the listing does not directly violate affordable housing rules, Denver’s housing policies are designed to create more **inclusive communities**. By focusing on exclusivity, the listing could perpetuate gentrification, which Denver is actively trying to combat.

Conclusion: Potential Compliance Issues in Denver, Colorado

- **Familial status** discrimination through the emphasis on two primary suites.
- **Lack of mention of accessibility** features, which could indicate non-compliance with disability accommodation standards.
- Language that might indirectly exclude **low-income** families and minorities by emphasizing **luxury** and **affluence** in the Cherry Creek area, potentially conflicting with **Denver’s anti-gentrification efforts**.

- **Energy efficiency omissions**, which might raise questions about **Denver's green building** mandates if this is a newer or renovated property.

Reforming the listing to address these issues ensures compliance with Denver's local laws and federal housing regulations, while also promoting a more inclusive, diverse, and equitable housing market.

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